

Interaction of Monoprotic Ligands with Metal Ions

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A new simpler method of calculation of free ligand concentration and so formation constant for metal complexes have been applied to systems Cu(II)-acetate, Cu(II)-thiophene-2-carboxylic acid, Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde in aqueous, aq-ethanol (50%V/V) and aq-dioxan (50%V/V) media. Calculations of [L] and K_n by new method is done and compared with the values obtained by the former method. In aq. solution the values are similar but in mixed aq. media some small discrepancies are observed. For salicylaldehyde ligand calculations are done on both the bases

$$K_1 = \frac{[ML][H]}{[M][HL]} \text{ (new) and } K_1 = \frac{[ML]}{[M][L]} \text{ (former),}$$

once again excellent correlations are obtained between the two methods in aqueous medium.

It has been shown in a previous communication¹ that the free ligand exponent can be calculated by the simple expression

$$pL = \log_{10} \left\{ \frac{1}{(T_L^0 - \bar{n} T_M^0)(1 - \bar{n}_A)} \times \frac{V^0 + V'''}{V^0} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where T_L^0 and T_M^0 are initial concentrations of ligand and metal respectively and $\bar{n}_A$ is the proton-ligand formation function, V^0 is the initial volume and V''' is volume of alkali added for metal titration.

The expression (1) does not involve $C\beta_1^H$ or [H], so the calculation of pL (or [L]) becomes much simpler. And that the final calculations of formation constant can be made completely from the experimental data. In aq. dioxan medium $P\beta_1^H$ or B values are also not required. Irving and Rossotti's² pH titration technique, is simple to manipulate, as well as, elegant, for the measurement of complex formation constants. But it was so long applicable in aqueous, aq. dioxan, and aq. ethanol media only. Measurements in other mixed aqueous solvents in other methods^{3,4} involve much elaborate and laborious calculations. It appears that the expression (1) serves to extend the applicability of Irving and Rossotti's technique to all non-reactive mixed aqueous solvents, whenever monoprotic ligands are involved. In the present paper we attempt to demonstrate the experimental basis of this method.

Systems selected for the study are Cu(II)-Acetate in both water and water-dioxan (50% V/V), Cu(II)-Thiophene-2-carboxylate in water-dioxan (50% V/V) and Cu(II)-Salicylaldehyde in water, water-dioxan (50% V/V) and water-ethanol (50% V/V). The data for all these are calculated both by the present and former methods and they are compared. $\bar{n}$ and $\bar{n}_A$ are calculated from the experimental curves³. $C\beta_1^H$ and $P\beta_1^H$

are calculated for the ligands by the usual methods, these being used to calculate pL (or [L]) by the former methods.

Assuming maximum coordination number 2 the expression⁵

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)[L]} = \frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(\bar{n}-1)} \beta_2 - \beta_1 \quad (2)$$

is used to calculate the formation constants.

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)[L]} (= Y)$$

is plotted against $\frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(\bar{n}-1)} (= X)$ in large graph

papers and the points which fall on approximate straight lines are used for calculation of K_n by the method of least squares.

When $\bar{n}_A \rightarrow 1$ and $[L] \rightarrow 0$

The equations¹,

$$[HL] = T_{HL} - \bar{n} T_M \quad (3)$$

$$\text{and } \sum_{n=0}^{n=\bar{n}} (\bar{n}-n) \beta_n \frac{[HL]^n}{[H]^n} = 0 \quad (4)$$

are used to calculate the formation constants. This situation is very well represented by Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde system in aq. alcohol [Fig. 1]. At the point X, bifurcation of the mineral acid and ligand curve starts whereas the metal curve separates at a much lower pH region.

In the pH titration curves for the above system in water or water-dioxan media the point of bifurcation is not so well marked. That is, a very narrow separation is observed between the curves from a lower pH region. Despite this fact, values for these systems

Fig. 1. : pH titration curve for Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde system in 50% V/V water-ethanol medium.

also are calculated both in the new and former methods, and very good comparisons could be made.

Experimental

All reagents are of A. R. or G. R. grade. Thio-phen-2-carboxylic acid is used as received from Fluka A. G., dioxan is purified⁶ and ethanol dehydrated and distilled. Copper perchlorate solution is prepared by the usual method⁷. The pH titration is carried out in nitrogen atmosphere with a bench model Cambridge pH meter at a temperature $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$.

The solution for metal titration is 20 ml of the solvent containing 0.001 M Cu(II) ion, 0.005 M ligand and 0.1 M NaClO₄ and 0.0025 M HClO₄. The solutions for ligand and mineral acid titrations are the same as above but without the metal for the former and without metal and ligand for the latter. The titrant is 0.1 M carbonate free NaOH solution.

To ascertain the actual pH in the mixed aq-solvent 20 ml of 0.0025 M HClO₄ in a particular solvent is titrated with 0.1 M NaOH (also dissolved in the same solvent). Near the neutralisation point the alkali strength is reduced to 0.01M and the titration continued. The pH meter readings are noted. A similar titration is done in aqueous medium. The same ionic strength, is maintained (0.1M NaClO₄) in all the titrations. Correlation is made on the basis of the same volume of alkali added to aqueous and mixed aqueous solvents. [Fig 2].

The points fall on good straight lines. The pH corresponding to the pH meter reading in some solvent can be read off from the graph. Theoretically calculated pH for the aqueous solution slightly differs from the actual pH because of the effect of ionic strength and

Fig. 2. : pH meter reading and actual pH (aqueous) correlation for mixed aqueous media.

therefore correlation with the experimental pH appeared to be more justified.

$\bar{n}$, pH (or B), and [L], Y and X values in two methods for the systems are shown in the tables 2 to 7. The values of formation constants are given in table 1. In the tables

$$Y = \frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)} [L] ; X = \frac{(2-\bar{n}) [L]}{(\bar{n}-1)}$$

$$Y' = \frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)} \frac{[H]}{[HL]} ; X' = \frac{(2-\bar{n}) [HL]}{(\bar{n}-1) [H]}$$

Results and Discussion

For Cu(II)-Acetate system (Table 2) in aqueous solution the [L] values and therefore the Y and X values closely resemble in both the new and former methods of calculation. Theoretically [L] should be equal in both the methods. Small differences occur, because in the present calculations the data used are entirely from the experimental curves but in the former method the experimental values are mixed up with calculated values ($C\beta_1^H$). The Y/X curves run closely parallel and K_1 and K_2 values are nearly equal when calculated by the two methods (Table 1). Although the $\bar{n}$ values are low indicating weak complex formation the Y/X curve shows a definite slope after $\bar{n}=0.82$. Therefore K_2 is calculated. It is interesting that $K_2 > K_1$. The values are justified as the standard deviation $\alpha = .006$ is small.

$$\alpha = \left[\frac{\sum (\bar{n}_{\text{exp}} - \bar{n}_{\text{calc}})^2}{N} \right]^{1/2}$$

N = number of observations.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL-LIGAND SYSTEMS IN AQUEOUS AND MIXED-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS CALCULATED BY TWO DIFFERENT METHODS AT 30° ± .1° WITH 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH.

System	Medium	New method		Former method	
		K ₁ (log K ₁)*	K ₂ (log K ₂)	K ₁ (log K ₁)	K ₂ (log K ₂)
Cu(II)-Acetate	Water	57.8994 (1.7636)	146.79 (2.1667)	58.689 (1.768)	136.064 (2.1335)
	Water-dioxan, 50% V/V	1355.166 (3.1319)	299.811 (2.4769)	1464.59 (3.1652)	224.9958 (2.3521)
	Cu(II)-Thiophene- 2-carboxylate	Water-dioxan, 50% V/V	409.2797 (2.6119)	329.6323 (2.5180)	438.7828 (2.6422)
Cu(II)-Salicyl- aldehyde	Water	1.3172 × 10 ⁻⁸ (3.1204)	6.593 × 10 ⁻⁶ (5.8155)	2.9051 × 10 ⁵ (5.4631)	1.3109 × 10 ⁴ (4.1204)
	Water-dioxan 50% V/V	3.2626 × 10 ⁻⁸ (3.5135)	9.106 × 10 ⁻⁵ (5.9593)	1.2405 × 10 ⁶ (6.0934)	8.762 × 10 ⁵ (5.9426)
	Water-ethanol, 50% V/V	3.8074 × 10 ⁻⁸ (3.5806)	1.851 × 10 ⁻⁴ (4.2674)	2.6136 × 10 ⁶ (6.4171)	8.480 × 10 ⁴ (4.9284)

* From the scatter of point along the Y/X lines the log K values vary within ±.01 to ±.03 in log units.

TABLE 2—DATA FOR Cu(II)-ACETATE-WATER SYSTEM AT 30° ± .1°, WITH 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH CALCULATED BY TWO METHODS. log Cβ₁^H FOR HAC=4.7351.

pH	$\bar{n}$	[L] × 10 ⁻³	New Method		[L] × 10 ⁻³	Former Method	
			-Y	-X × 10 ⁻³		-Y	-XX10 ⁻³
3.6	.02196	0.4121	54.4843	.08334	0.4104	54.7100	0.08299
3.7	.03356	0.4956	70.0672	.10084	0.5035	68.9678	0.10244
3.8	.04325	0.6240	72.4441	.12762	0.6148	73.5281	0.12573
3.9	.05223	0.7430	74.1700	.15269	0.7466	73.8123	0.15343
4.0	.06198	0.9147	72.2371	.18885	0.9001	73.4044	0.18596
4.1	.07081	1.087	70.1068	.2257	1.080	70.5612	0.2241
4.2	.08262	1.289	69.8687	.2694	1.275	70.6359	0.26647
4.25	.095	1.385	75.8452	.2915	1.384	75.900	0.29133
4.3	.1119	1.48	85.13 ⁷	.31463	1.486	84.7909	0.31592
4.35	.1274	1.586	92.0557	.3404	1.636	89.2422	0.35107
4.4	.1431	1.691	98.7565	.3664	1.713	97.4882	0.37119

TABLE 3—DATA FOR Cu(II)-ACETATE-WATER-DIOXAN (50% V/V) SYSTEM AT 30° ± .1° WITH 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH. CALCULATED BY THE TWO METHODS.

log Pβ₁^H for HAC = 6.084.

B	$\bar{n}$	[L] × 10 ⁻⁴	New Method		[L] × 10 ⁻⁴	Former Method	
			-Y	-X × 10 ⁻³		-Y	-X × 10 ⁻³
4.2	.0891	.7800	1253.4243	.1636	.6246	1565.2754	0.1310
4.3	.1074	.8816	1364.2018	.187	.7891	1524.8080	0.1673
4.4	.1279	1.045	1403.4201	.2243	.9620	1524.5052	0.2065
4.5	.1583	1.275	1475.0721	.2789	1.197	1571.1921	0.2618
4.6	.1986	1.553	1593.6739	.3495	1.484	1669.9213	0.3335
4.7	.2404	1.940	1631.3520	.4493	1.827	1732.2512	0.4231
4.8	.2808	2.337	1670.6623	.5586	2.262	1726.0557	0.5406
4.9	.3283	2.856	1711.3438	.7107	2.755	1774.0827	0.6855
5.0	.3799	3.403	1800.3029	.889	3.486	1757.4386	0.9106
5.1	.4243	4.161	1771.2468	1.1388	4.159	1772.0985	1.1382
5.2	.4922	5.009	1935.0753	1.4873	5.031	1926.6134	1.4936
5.3	.5543	6.003	2071.7334	1.9471	6.042	2058.3608	1.9596
5.4	.6222	7.079	2326.4629	2.5816	7.391	2228.2547	2.6953
5.5	.7046	8.252	2890.4996	3.4996	8.517	2800.5639	3.7345

Data for Cu(II)-Acetate system in aq. dioxan (Table 3) show some discrepancy in [L] calculated by the two methods. There is some amount to arbitrariness^a in the Pβ₁^H values used in the former method; Pβ₁^H = Cβ₁^H / f × u_H⁰ where f is the activity coefficient of [H] in the solvent mixture and u_H⁰ corresponds to the correction at zero ionic strength and undergo some

change with the change of the composition of the solvent mixture when titration progresses. This change is rapid especially above 50% V/V for water-dioxan medium^{8,9}. Therefore it seems that the values obtained by the new method is more acceptable. The discrepancies in log K₁ and log K₂ value are not however very large (Table 1).

TABLE 4—DATA FOR Cu(II)-THIOPHENE-2-CARBOXYLATE, WATER-DIOXAN (50% V/V) SYSTEM IN $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ WITH 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH, CALCULATED BY TWO METHODS.

$P\beta_1^H$ for Thiophene-2-carboxylic acid = 4.9987.

B	$\bar{n}$	New Method			Former Method		
		$[L] \times 10^{-3}$	-Y	$-X \times 10^{-3}$	$[L] \times 10^{-3}$	-Y	$-X \times 10^{-3}$
3.5	.0650	0.1694	410.5844	0.3505	0.1489	467.1121	0.3081
3.6	.0839	0.2042	448.4422	0.4270	0.1845	496.3301	0.3858
3.7	.1079	0.2440	495.6987	0.5175	0.2283	529.7875	0.4841
3.8	.1284	0.3016	488.4456	0.6476	0.2822	522.0241	0.6058
3.9	.1578	0.3631	516.0187	0.7142	0.3475	539.1838	0.7600
4.0	.1874	0.4258	541.6104	0.9497	0.4259	541.4832	0.9499
4.1	.2367	0.5181	598.2212	1.1965	0.5178	598.8814	1.1961
4.2	.2930	0.6247	663.4018	1.5082	0.6323	655.4279	1.5265
4.3	.3538	0.7729	708.3820	1.9689	0.7489	731.0836	1.9077
4.4	.4051	0.9260	735.3322	2.4225	0.8910	764.2589	2.3806
4.5	.4686	1.098	803.1162	3.1642	1.052	838.2334	3.031
4.6	.5403	1.266	928.3821	4.0199	1.223	961.0134	4.1226
4.7	.6080	1.433	1082.3589	5.0886	1.405	1103.9291	4.9890
4.8	.6860	1.624	1345.2668	6.7959	1.595	1369.7262	6.6745

In Cu(II) thiophene-2-carboxylic acid system (Table 4) in aq. dioxan the differences in the data calculated by the two methods are evident. Here again the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ obtained by two methods are not much different.

For salicylaldehyde, $\log C\beta_1^H$ is very high for the OH group, 8.34 in aqueous and 9.41 in aq. dioxan media. For such systems equations (3,4) become applicable. Data for the system Cu(II)-salicylaldehyde in aq. alcohol are shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5—DATA FOR Cu(II)-SALICYLALDEHYDE-WATER-ETHANOL SYSTEM (50% V/V) AT $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ WITH 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH, CALCULATED BY THE TWO METHODS.

$\log P\beta_1^H$ of Salicylaldehyde = 9.1486.

B	pH	$\bar{n}$	New Method			Former Method		
			$[HL] \times 10^{-3}$	$Y' \times 10^{-3}$	X'	$[L] \times 10^{-5}$	$Y \times 10^7$	$X \times 10^{-5}$
4.00	3.72	.05018	4.949	-2.0202	-53.3385	.003440	-.15357	-.007062
4.30	4.02	.1354	4.8646	-3.0629	-109.8523	.006733	-.23259	-.01452
4.60	4.31	.2605	4.7299	-3.6156	-227.5030	.013060	-.26973	-.03072
4.90	4.51	.4308	4.5622	-4.5303	-458.0509	.02433	-.3111	-.0671
5.20	4.83	.6110	4.389	-5.1948	-1066.1020	.04821	-.3258	-.1721
5.50	5.11	.7962	4.2038	-7.2132	-3199.0079	.09160	-.4265	-.6411
6.10	5.66	1.132	3.868	+4.849	+11624.6801	.3339	+2.568	+2.1966
6.40	5.95	1.291	3.709	+1.3413	+8053.8324	.6655	+0.666	+1.6214
6.70	6.23	1.455	3.545	+0.5311	+7211.4470	1.211	+0.264	+1.451

TABLE 6—DATA FOR Cu(II)-SALICYLALDEHYDE-WATER SYSTEM AT $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ WITH 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH, CALCULATED BY THE TWO METHODS.

$\log C\beta_1^H$ of Salicylaldehyde = 8.336.

pH	$\bar{n}$	New Method			Former Method		
		$[HL] \times 10^{-3}$	$Y' \times 10^{-3}$	X'	$[L] \times 10^{-6}$	$Y \times 10_6$	$X \times 10^{-6}$
4.1	0.0462	4.9538	-0.7731	-127.7079	0.2809	-1.68216	-0.5750
4.2	0.0708	4.9291	-0.9535	-162.1878	0.3518	-2.1451	-0.7301
4.3	0.1063	4.8937	-1.2158	-206.8929	0.4395	-2.6750	-0.9306
4.4	0.1520	4.848	-1.4707	-265.3851	0.5476	-3.2302	-1.1920
4.5	0.1824	4.819	-1.4619	-338.7789	0.6848	-3.2141	-1.5203
4.6	0.2232	4.7768	-1.5091	-434.9574	0.8553	-3.3092	-1.9526
4.7	0.2754	4.7246	-1.6022	-563.6534	1.066	-3.3943	-2.5177
4.8	0.3149	4.6851	-1.5546	-727.0447	1.328	-3.3957	-3.2548
4.9	0.3591	4.6409	-1.5191	-943.7648	1.655	-3.3372	-4.2240
5.0	0.4121	4.5879	-1.5039	-1239.1700	2.060	-3.3193	-5.5286
5.1	0.4683	4.5317	-1.5433	-1643.5477	2.560	-3.3450	-7.3121
5.2	0.5244	4.4756	-1.5539	-2200.6022	3.183	-3.3534	-9.7635
5.3	0.5861	4.4139	-1.6074	-3008.3798	3.949	-3.4485	-13.2758
5.4	0.6528	4.3472	-1.7211	-4237.0509	4.769	-4.0016	-18.6404
5.5	0.7092	4.2908	-1.7966	-6023.3080	6.144	-3.7458	-26.4279
5.6	0.7716	4.2284	-2.0066	-9053.0254	7.546	-4.9257	-43.1403
5.7	0.8433	4.1567	-2.582	-15380.0416	9.328	-5.1862	-63.7821
5.8	0.9153	4.0847	-4.1909	-33003.2813	11.54	-7.7558	-126.3658
6.1	1.112	3.888	+2.0276	+38824.0365	21.91	+5.4719	+218.8592

TABLE 7—DATA FOR Cu(II)-SALICYLALDEHYDE-WATER-DIOXAN (50% V/V) SYSTEM AT $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ WITH 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH, CALCULATED BY THE TWO METHODS.

$\log P\beta_1^H$ of Salicylaldehyde=9.41.

B	pH	$\bar{n}$	[HL] × 10 ⁻³	New Method Y' × 10 ⁻³	X'	[L] × 10 ⁻³	Former Method Y × 10 ⁻³	X × 10 ⁻³
4.0	3.90	0.08024	4.9197	-2.2155	- 81.5631	1.843	-473.3592	-0.03846
4.3	4.19	0.1946	4.8054	-3.2463	-166.8246	3.585	-673.0721	-0.08036
4.6	4.48	0.3406	4.6594	-3.6700	-354.1383	6.926	-745.7841	-0.1743
4.9	4.78	0.5055	4.4945	-3.7601	-818.2813	13.30	-768.6049	-0.4019
5.2	5.07	0.6705	4.3295	-4.0002	-2052.5326	25.53	-797.0627	-1.0301
5.5	5.32	0.8206	4.1794	-5.2378	-5740.8990	49.08	-931.9755	-3.2266
6.1	5.95	1.161	3.839	+2.1073	+17830.4099	178.9	+403.0844	+9.3228
6.4	6.25	1.326	3.674	+0.6225	+13508.6928	341.2	+119.2115	+7.0542
6.7	6.54	1.498	3.502	+0.2477	+12240.3883	647.6	+46.4489	+6.5280

The values of $\log K_n$ differ from those of other media for obvious reasons but they are of the same order.

The data for aqueous medium for this system show excellent agreement between the two methods. The difference $\log K_n$ [former]— $\log K_n$ [new] should be equal to $\log C\beta_1^H$ of the ligand. Thus for this system (Table 1) $\log K_1$ (former)— $\log K_1$ (new)=8.34 and $\log K_2$ (former)— $\log K_2$ (new)=8.3049 and the experimental value is 8.336. The data for system aq. dioxan and aq. alcohol are given in tables V and VII respectively.

In aq. dioxan

$$\log K_1 \text{ (former)} - \log K_1 \text{ (new)} = 8.58$$

$$\text{and } \log K_2 \text{ (former)} - \log K_2 \text{ (new)} = 9.98$$

The experimental value of $\log P\beta_1^H = 9.41$. For the aq. ethanol medium

$$\log K_1 \text{ (former)} - \log K_1 \text{ (new)} = 8.836$$

$$\log K_2 \text{ (former)} - \log K_2 \text{ (new)} = 8.66$$

and the experimental value of $\log P\beta_1^H = 9.1486$.

These values show that the agreement is not good in mixed aqueous solvents. Same arguments as before can be advanced to account for this.

The experiments in the present paper prove the validity of the new method of calculation. The discrepancies of values with those from the former method can be explained more in favour of the present method. The main features may be summarised. For

monoprotic ligands :

- (1) This method provides a much simpler method of calculation and calculations can be done entirely from experimental curves.
- (2) Irving and Rossotti's technique can be applied to all non-reacting mixed aq. solvents.
- (3) Metal ligand interaction in different mixed aqueous solvents can be studied with greater ease and the solvent properties (dielectric constant etc) can be correlated with the equilibrium constants.

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